

Patterns of Local Currency Financing in the New Development Bank (2016-2025)

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Abstract

This paper analyzes the patterns of local currency financing in the New Development Bank (NDB) from 2016 to 2025. Based on an original database of 139 projects constructed through web scraping and adjusted for inflation and exchange rates, the study examines the currency composition of the NDB's portfolio across countries, areas of operation, sovereignty and time. The findings reveal that local currency loans represent 18% of total financing – notably higher than in other Multilateral Development Banks (MDBs) but still distant from the NDB's 30% target. Local currency lending is predominantly domestic: countries borrow almost exclusively in their own currencies, with the significant exception of four Renminbi-denominated projects in Brazil linked to Chinese-acquired energy companies, suggesting cross-border local currency financing follows Chinese foreign direct investment. The portfolio exhibits pronounced heterogeneity among BRICS members: China and South Africa have developed meaningful local currency pipelines, while India, Brazil, Russia, Bangladesh and Egypt show negligible or no local currency operations. The presence of EUR and CHF denominated projects in Russia, and EUR denominated projects in Brazil and China nuances the de-dollarization narrative, as the NDB sometimes replaces dollars with other core currencies rather than exclusively with BRICS currencies. These findings suggest that expanding local currency financing requires not only political commitment but also deeper financial markets and innovative risk management instruments.

Keywords: New Development Bank; Local Currency Financing; Finance for Development; De-dollarization.

Introduction

The BRICS have gained international attention due to their economic and demographic trends, which are frequently compared to those of the G7 in the literature (Carvalho et al., 2015; Mehra & Azharuddin, 2023). Another important feature emphasized in the literature is that the BRICS are creating a cooperation platform rooted in their dissatisfaction with Western-led Bretton Woods financial institutions (Carvalho et al., 2015), which have been widely criticized for their conditionalities, structural adjustment programs, and austerity measures [1]. In this context, the BRICS began to advocate for reforms in the global financial architecture, in which power-sharing is excessively slow or denied (Biswas, 2015; Qobo & Soko, 2015).

For this reason, the New Development Bank (NDB) was idealized in 2014 during the 6th BRICS Summit in Fortaleza, creating opportunities for intra-BRICS financial cooperation and addressing some of the global monetary-financial asymmetries (De Conti et al., 2019). In 2016, the NDB became officially operational. Designed to finance infrastructure and sustainable development projects (Molinari & Ceballos, 2024), the emergence of the NDB represents both a political and an economic shift (Biswas, 2015; Copper, 2017; Suchodolski & Demeulemeester, 2018). Its portfolio is closely aligned with infrastructure, renewable energy, and sustainable development projects, tailored to the challenges and specific needs of developing countries in the Global South (Copper, 2017; Mehra & Azharuddin, 2023).

A notable example is the NDB's local currency lending mechanism, which allows borrowers to take on debt in their own currencies, an important feature given the exchange-rate risks faced by developing countries (Carvalho et al., 2015; Suchodolski & Demeulemeester, 2018). This mechanism also creates opportunities to increase the use of BRICS currencies, positively affecting their liquidity and stability (De Conti et al., 2019). Additionally, it may also contribute to the maturation of local currency bond markets and is particularly relevant in the context of de-dollarization (De Conti et al., 2019).

Expanding local currency lending in Multilateral Development Banks (MDBs) can be seen as one way peripheral countries can obtain some relief from their international financial subordination. This is based on the idea that local currency financing can reduce destabilizing currency mismatches and the exposure of debt payments to exchange rates, which – in the event of depreciation – raises the nominal burden of debt and contributes to insolvency and default (Bonizzi et al., 2024). Therefore, expanding local currency lending can increase borrower creditworthiness and reduce associated risk. It also reduces pressure for generating and using foreign currency inflows to service debt, which generally occur in contexts of unfavorable exchange rates and imply high costs, convertibility risks, and balance-of-payments constraints (Bonizzi et al., 2024).

[1] See Babb & Kentikelenis (2018), Botta (2016), Botta (2018), Bracking (2009), Carvalho (2016), Chorev (2018), Libânio (2020), Stockhammer (2016) and Thirkell-White (2006).

It is important to note that the contemporary geopolitical context further intensifies the need for an alternative to the dollar hegemony. For instance, in early 2025, Donald Trump threatened to impose 100% tariffs on BRICS countries should they attempt to launch a de-dollarization process through a new BRICS currency (McKibbin & Noland, 2025). However, Trump fails to recognize that the BRICS already possess an initiative that creates opportunities for their members to reduce dependence on the dollar – the NDB's local currency lending mechanism. The literature tends to overlook this aspect of the NDB, focusing instead on its institutional innovations (e.g., loans without conditionalities, principle of equality, etc.). However, this mechanism is fundamental for promoting inclusive access to development financing while reducing the international financial subordination faced by peripheral countries (De Conti et al., 2019; Bonizzi et al., 2024).

The NDB has set an explicit target of reaching 30% of its loans in local currency (NDB, 2022), a goal still far from being met, as such loans account for only 18% of its total portfolio. Despite the theoretical benefits of local currency lending, its implementation within the NDB remains empirically understudied. This paper addresses this gap by quantitatively investigating the patterns of local currency financing across the bank's portfolio from 2016 to 2025. The following section outlines the methodology, succeeded by an analysis of the portfolio, and lastly a conclusion.

Methodology

In light of the considerable number of projects developed and the lack of a complete NDB database for the portfolio, publicly available information from the bank's website was collected and organized to understand the nuances between the projects' financing currency, country of implementation, areas of operation, and sovereignty of projects. The database was constructed through web scraping techniques, gathering for each development project (i) the country of implementation, (ii) the project status, (iii) the area of operation, (iv) the type of operation, (v) the financing approval date, (vi) the current limit of NDB financing – that is, the amount funded by the NDB – and (vii) the currency used for the operation [2].

The full portfolio of projects contains 157 projects, operating in China, Brazil, India, Russia, South Africa, Bangladesh and Egypt. For the analysis, it was opted to exclude projects that were cancelled (N=18), consequently maintaining all projects completed, approved and proposed between 2016 and 2025. With this specific selection, the final database contains 139 projects, split between different currencies – USD (94), RMB (28), EUR (8), ZAR (7), INR (1) and CHF (1) – and areas of operation.

In order to compare the projects more equitably, all projects' limit of financing were brought

[2] US Dollar (USD), Euro (EUR), Renminbi (RMB), South African Rand (ZAR), Indian Rupee (INR), and Swiss Franc (CHF) are present in the portfolio

to the latest present values in their respective currencies (e.g., Dollar, Renminbi, Rand, Euro, Indian Rupee, and Swiss Franc), using each country's specific Current Price Index [4] (CPI), and then converted to dollars, using the December 2025 exchange rate. This process relied upon several databases [5] including:

1. For the CPIs: National Bureau of Statistics of China (RMB), Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis (EUR, USD, and INR), Department of Statistics of the Republic of South Africa (ZAR), and the Swiss Federal Statistical Office (CHF).
2. For the conversion: Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis (RMB), the online foreign exchange rate database of Xenon Laboratories (ZAR, CHF, and INR), the European Central Bank (EUR).

Overview of the NBD Portfolio (2016-2025)

Since becoming operational in 2016, the NDB has approved a total of USD 44.89 billion in financing across 139 projects implemented in its seven member countries. India is the largest borrower, receiving USD 12.03 billion (26.8% of the total portfolio), followed by China with USD 9.72 billion (21.7%), Brazil with USD 8.21 billion (18.3%), and South Africa with USD 8.05 billion (17.9%). Russia, Bangladesh, and Egypt complete the portfolio with smaller shares of 12.2%, 2.7%, and 0.5%, respectively (see Table 1 and Figure 1 in the annex [6]).

The concentration of financing in the founding members reflects the NDB's initial mandate, while the inclusion of Bangladesh and Egypt signals the bank's gradual expansion into the broader Global South. In terms of sectors, Transport Infrastructure dominates the portfolio with USD 16.1 billion (36% of total), followed by COVID-19 Emergency Assistance with USD 10.8 billion (24.1%), and Multiple Areas projects with USD 6.1 billion (13.6%) (see Table 2). This sectoral distribution aligns with the NDB's founding objective of financing infrastructure and sustainable development, with the pandemic-related spike representing an exceptional countercyclical response.

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Currency Composition

[6] All tables and figures can be found in the annex at the end of the paper

The currency composition analysis reveals a portfolio still heavily dependent on core currencies yet showing meaningful progress in local currency financing. Of the total USD 44.89 billion, USD-denominated loans account for USD 33.44 billion (74.5% of the portfolio), distributed across 94 projects. RMB emerges as the largest alternative, representing USD 5.93 billion (13.2%) across 28 projects, followed by EUR with USD 2.69 billion (6.0%) in 8 projects. The South African Rand (ZAR) follows with USD 2.15 billion (4.8%) in 7 projects, while CHF (1.49% in 1 project) and INR (0.0003% in 1 project) occupy marginal positions (see Table 3).

The data confirms the NDB's self-positioning as the most advanced MDB in local currency financing (Bonizzi et al., 2024). Local currencies (RMB, ZAR, INR) together represent 18.01% of the portfolio by value – precisely the figure mentioned in the introduction and still distant from the 30% target set by the bank (NDB, 2022). However, this aggregate figure masks significant heterogeneity across members and over time.

The temporal analysis (see Chart 1) reveals important fluctuations in currency composition. In the bank's inaugural year (2016), RMB loans already represented 22% of approvals, demonstrating early commitment to local currency financing. The years 2017 and 2018 saw a retreat to 0% and 20% respectively, possibly reflecting institutional learning curves. A significant diversification occurred in 2019, when ZAR (17%), RMB (9%), and CHF (12%) entered the portfolio, reducing USD share to 62%. The peak of ZAR financing in 2024 (32%) suggests South Africa's growing role in the portfolio and potential maturation of its local currency borrowing mechanisms.

When classifying currencies between "Core" (USD, EUR, CHF) and "Peripheral" (RMB, ZAR, INR), a gradual trend emerges (see Chart 2). Despite yearly fluctuations, peripheral currencies show a modest upward trend, from approximately 12% in 2016 to 27% in 2025 (linear projection).

Geographical Patterns

A critical finding emerges when crossing currency use with implementing countries. Local currency financing is overwhelmingly – though not exclusively – domestic. The 28 RMB projects (USD 5.93 billion) are mostly implemented in China. South Africa's 7 ZAR projects (USD 2.15 billion) are all implemented in South Africa. The single INR project (a mere USD 147,414) is in India. However, a significant exception exists: four RMB-denominated projects totaling USD 137 million (approximately 2% of the portfolio) are implemented in Brazil. These are non-sovereign operations financing energy companies acquired by Chinese interests, suggesting that RMB internationalization through the NDB occurs where Chinese strategic investments create demand for renminbi financing even outside China's borders.

This pattern reveals a fundamental characteristic of the NDB's local currency mechanism: it

sometimes replaces it with other core currencies (EUR, CHF) rather than exclusively with BRICS currencies (see Figure 2 and Chart 3).

Sectoral Patterns

The sectoral data reveals that Transport Infrastructure is the primary vehicle for local currency financing (see Table 4 and Figure 3). Of all ZAR-denominated financing, 81% is directed at transport projects. For RMB, transport represents 43% of sectoral allocation, second only to COVID-19 emergency assistance (35%). The single CHF project (100% transport) and a significant portion of EUR financing (55% transport) reinforce this pattern.

This sectoral concentration is theoretically coherent. Transport infrastructure projects – such as roads, railways, and ports – typically generate revenues in local currency (tolls, fees, local taxes) and have long gestation periods. Financing them in local currency avoids currency mismatches between revenue streams (local currency) and debt servicing (foreign currency). The predominance of local currency in this sector suggests the NDB is effectively applying the principle of matching currency composition with project cash flows.

Conversely, Clean Energy projects show a more balanced currency distribution, with significant USD (10%) and EUR (27%) participation alongside RMB (17%) and the sole INR project. This may reflect the import content of renewable energy equipment (solar panels, wind turbines), which often requires foreign currency for international suppliers – a practical constraint on local currency financing.

Sovereignty of Operations

An additional dimension of analysis concerns the nature of the borrower. The data distinguishes between sovereign and non-sovereign operations across currencies (see Chart 4). Strikingly, local currency operations are overwhelmingly sovereign guaranteed: 98% of RMB and 93% of ZAR financing carry sovereign guarantees. In contrast, USD operations have a significant non-sovereign component (18%). This pattern suggests that the NDB's local currency lending currently relies on government balance sheets to mitigate currency and credit risks. Private sector borrowers, when accessing NDB financing, still considerably receive dollars – the currency in which the bank's own capital is largely denominated.

This finding has important implications. While sovereign-guaranteed local currency lending protects the bank's balance sheet, it limits the mechanism's reach into the private sector, where currency mismatches are often most acute. Expanding local currency financing to non-sovereign borrowers would require deeper domestic capital markets and hedging instruments.

Discussion

The empirical patterns reveal both achievements and limitations in the NDB's local currency strategy. On one hand, the bank has successfully deployed 18% of its portfolio in local currencies – a figure unmatched by other MDBs. The concentration in transport infrastructure demonstrates strategic alignment with development finance best practices. The gradual upward trend in peripheral currencies suggests institutional commitment to the goal.

On the other hand, three puzzles emerge. First, domestic confinement: local currency lending remains largely trapped within national borders. BRICS currencies are not yet being lent across borders in any meaningful way, limiting the mechanism's potential for true internationalization. Second, sovereign reliance: the near absence of non-sovereign local currency operations suggests the mechanism has not yet penetrated private sector balance sheets. Third, and most strikingly, heterogeneity among BRICS members: while China and South Africa have developed robust local currency pipelines, India's INR participation remains negligible, and Brazil, Russia, Bangladesh, and Egypt have no local currency operations at all.

This heterogeneity requires explanation. China's deep capital markets and internationalized currency enable RMB lending, while South Africa's developed financial system facilitates ZAR operations. In contrast, India, Brazil, and Russia have no meaningful local currency presence in the NDB portfolio despite their large economies. Exchange rate volatility in the Real, Rupee, and Ruble discourages lenders from providing financing in local currencies. The absence of deep long-term swap markets makes hedging prohibitively expensive for infrastructure maturities, while high domestic interest rates in Brazil and Russia create a disincentive – dollar loans often appear cheaper even accounting for depreciation risk. Pipeline composition also matters. Projects with high import content may require foreign currency financing regardless of borrower preferences. For Russia, geopolitical sanctions have further constrained local currency options.

Finally, the distance to the 30% target (currently 18%) raises questions about feasibility. At the current pace of approximately 1-2 percentage points annual increase in peripheral currency share, the target would be reached around 2028-2030 – later than initially envisioned. The current geopolitical turmoil (e.g., Ukraine and Iran wars, reescalation of Trump's trade war, Gaza's invasion, etc.) may paradoxically accelerate this process by creating political impetus to reduce dollar dependence. However, the structural constraints identified here – domestic confinement, sovereign reliance, and member heterogeneity – suggest that reaching 30% will require more than political will; it will demand innovations in risk management, currency swap arrangements, and cross-border local currency settlement mechanisms.

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ANNEX

Table 1 – Limit of NDB Financing (USD/% of USD/Number of Projects) by Country (2016-2025)

Country	Limit of NDB Financing (USD)	Limit of NDB Financing (% of USD)	Number of Projects
Bangladesh	1.194.261.412	2,66%	5
Brazil	8.213.925.287	18,30%	27
China	9.717.819.683	21,65%	38
Egypt	208.311.210	0,46%	1
India	12.031.165.940	26,80%	38
Russia	5.472.835.658	12,19%	14
South Africa	8.047.337.643	17,93%	16
Grand Total	44.885.656.833	100%	139

Author's own elaboration

Table 2 – Limit of NDB Financing (USD/% of USD/Number of Projects) by Area of Operation (2016-2025)

Area of Operation	Limit of NDB Financing (USD)	Limit of NDB Financing (% of USD)	Number of Projects
Clean Energy and Energy Efficiency	5.227.653.370	11,65%	27
COVID-19 Emergency Assistance	10.801.139.288	24,06%	9
Digital Infrastructure	373.253.830	0,83%	1
Environmental Protection	1.118.234.351	2,49%	5
Multiple Areas	6.099.910.037	13,59%	22
Social Infrastructure	1.565.497.869	3,49%	7
Transport Infrastructure	16.143.753.536	35,97%	49
Water and Sanitation	3.556.214.551	7,92%	19
Grand Total	44.885.656.833	100%	139

Author's own elaboration

Table 3 – Limit of NDB Financing (USD/% of USD/Number of Projects) by Currency (2016-2025)

Currency	Limit of NDB Financing (USD)	Limit of NDB Financing (% of USD)	Number of Projects
CHF	670.640.135	1,49%	1
EUR	2.692.363.487	6,00%	8
INR	147.414	0,0003%	1
RMB	5.934.201.303	13,22%	28
USD	33.439.701.139	74,50%	94
ZAR	2.148.603.355	4,79%	7
Grand Total	44.885.656.833	100%	139

Author's own elaboration

Table 4 – Share (% of USD) of Currencies in Different Areas of Operation (2016-2025)

	CHF	EUR	INR	RMB	USD	ZAR
Clean Energy and Energy Efficiency	0%	27%	100%	17%	10%	4%
COVID-19 Emergency Assistance	0%	0%	0%	35%	26%	0%
Digital Infrastructure	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%
Environmental Protection	0%	0%	0%	0%	3%	0%
Multiple Areas	0%	18%	0%	4%	16%	3%
Social Infrastructure	0%	0%	0%	0%	5%	0%
Transport Infrastructure	100%	55%	0%	43%	29%	81%
Water and Sanitation	0%	0%	0%	2%	10%	12%

Author’s own elaboration

Figure 1 – Map of the Limit of NDB Financing (adjusted in current USD) in Different Member Countries (2016-2025)

Author’s own elaboration

Figure 2 – Sankey Diagram of Project’s Portfolio Volume and Distribution (adjusted in current USD), by Country of Implementation and Currency (2016-2025)

Figure 3 – Sankey Diagram of Volume and Distribution of the Project Portfolio (adjusted in current USD), by Country of Implementation, Operation Area, and Currency (2016-2025)

Chart 1 – Share (% of USD) of Currencies in Total Funding of Projects

Author's own elaboration

Chart 2 – Share (% of USD) of the Utilization of Core- and Peripheral-currencies

Author's own elaboration

Chart 3 – Share of Currencies in Total Funding of Projects per Country (2016-2025)

Author's own elaboration

Chart 4 – Share of Project Sovereignty by Different Currencies (2016-2025)

Author's own elaboration